

THE CONCEPT OF A PERFECT HUMAN IN EASTERN THOUGHT

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Abstract. *The article explores the concept of the perfect human in Eastern thought. The term "perfect human" was first used in the works of Ibn Arabi. However, meanings expressing this concept can also be found in earlier works. The article provides a definition of the perfect human, explains terms conveying similar meanings, and discusses the status and virtues of the perfect human. Furthermore, as the Perfect Human is considered the "speaking Qur'an" (Qur'an Nāṭiq) and his character is identified with the Qur'an, the entire Qur'an can be viewed as the written embodiment of the Perfect Human. Its chapters and verses symbolize the stages and ascensions of this individual.*

Keywords: *perfect human, Muhammad, Hallaj, Nasafi, Ibn Arabi*

Introduction

The term Perfect Human is a mystical concept referring to someone who embodies the fullest manifestation of God's divine names and attributes. Various ideas and theories proposed throughout history regarding this concept have made it challenging to provide a comprehensive and universally accepted definition. Nevertheless, considering the perspectives and thoughts presented in the works of mystics, it can be said that the Perfect Human is one who is adorned with divine virtues, serves as the ultimate purpose of creation, is the cause of the universe's existence and continuation, and is fully realized in the comprehensive name of Allah. This individual acts as a mediator between the Divine and creation, is the indisputable vicegerent of God, whose knowledge of Sharia, the spiritual path (Tariqah), and ultimate truth (Haqiqah) is certain, and in whom good words, deeds, and virtues have reached their peak.

The Perfect Human is both a guide for humanity in appearance and essence, familiar with the spiritual and psychological ailments of individuals, and a healer of these afflictions. While being a creation of God, they embody God-like qualities. The divine attributes and virtues manifested in them represent the deputation of the Divine Essence, achieving such a rank by transcending duality and attaining essential unity with God's exalted identity.

The concept of the "Perfect Human" (Insān al-Kāmil), also referred to by titles such as the Universal Being (Kawn Jāmi'), the Pole of the World (Qutb al-'Ālam), the All-Reflecting Mirror (Jām-e Jahān-Namā), the Caliph (Khalīfa), the Imam, the Lord of the Age (Şāhib al-Zamān), the Great Elixir (Iksir al-A'zam), Khidr, Mahdi, the Complete, the Perfecter, the Wise, the Matured, and others, is a mystical term. It refers to one who is the most perfect manifestation of the divine names and attributes (Asmā' Ḥusnā) and a complete mirror of God. This individual is distinguished in Sharia, Tariqa, and Haqiqa, excels in virtuous words, deeds, and morals, and is unparalleled in divine knowledge.

Concepts Related to the Perfect Human

Although this term is not explicitly used in the Qur'an, its meaning can be inferred from verses that refer to the concepts of "God's vicegerent" (Khalīfat Allāh), Imam, purified ones (Muṭahhar), chosen ones (Mukhlāṣ), rightly guided (Muhtadī), truthful (Şiddīq), righteous (Şāliḥ), near to God (Muqarrab), forerunners (Sābiq), chosen ones (Muṣṭafā and Muḥtabā), the friends of God (Walī Allāh), messenger (Rasūl), prophet (Nabī), and those possessing a tranquil soul (Nafs Muṭma'innah) and complete servitude ('Ubūdiyyah Tāmmah). (Shirazi, p.407-408, Arabi, p. 392) Additionally, since the Perfect Human epitomizes all perfections, all Qur'anic verses that discuss human virtues and excellences can be associated with the Perfect Human.

Furthermore, as the Perfect Human is considered the "speaking Qur'an" (Qur'an Nāṭiq) and his character is identified with the Qur'an, the entire Qur'an can be viewed as the written

embodiment of the Perfect Human. Its chapters and verses symbolize the stages and ascensions of this individual.

Characteristics of the Lowest Existential Level of the Perfect Human

Although the Perfect Human, due to the lowest level of his existence, introduces himself as a human like others by God's command: "Say, 'I am only a human being like you.'" [Quran 18:110]

He says: "I am unaware of the unseen and, thus, deprived of many blessings, and misfortunes happen to me: 'If I had knowledge of the unseen, I would have gathered much good, and no harm would have touched me.'" [Quran 7:188]

He also admits ignorance of his own and others' fate: "I do not know what will be done with me or with you." [Quran 46:9]

And, as necessitated by life in the material world, he uses other beings, walks in the markets like others, and requires food and drink: "They said, 'What is this messenger who eats food and walks in the markets?'" [Quran 25:7].

However, due to his other dimensions and existential stages, he possesses ranks and virtues [Fanari, 1363, p. 338-339] that are beyond the comprehension of ordinary human understanding and the scope of this discussion. Therefore, here we will only briefly address some of these virtues.

Ranks and Virtues of the Perfect Human

Unity and Oneness

The Perfect Human, in essence, is a singular truth [Fanari, 1363, p. 337], which is referred to in mysticism as "Haqiqah Muhammadiyah" (The Muhammadan Reality). However, this singular truth, according to varying circumstances and diverse potentials, manifests in different forms and appearances over time [Kharezmi, 1364, p. 128]. These manifestations and appearances are none other than the forms of the prophets and infallible saints.

Thus, while the Qur'an acknowledges the superiority of some prophets over others: "Those messengers—We caused some of them to excel others." [Quran 2:253], it introduces all the prophets as united and supportive of one another: "And [remember] when Jesus, son of Mary, said, 'O Children of Israel, indeed I am the messenger of Allah to you, confirming what came before me of the Torah and bringing good tidings of a messenger to come after me, whose name is Ahmad.'" [Quran 61:6].

It does not recognize any division between them: "The believers... all of them have believed in Allah, His angels, His books, and His messengers, [saying], 'We make no distinction between any of His messengers.'" [Quran 2:285].

This idea is also cryptically mentioned in some narrations. For instance, a narration from Imam Ali ibn Abi Talib (peace be upon him) states:

"The first thing the Almighty God created was the light of His beloved Muhammad (peace be upon him and his family)... Then, God created twenty seas from the light of Muhammad, all of which were made of light. He then commanded the light of Muhammad to descend into those seas. When it emerged from the last sea, God said: 'O My beloved! O Master of My prophets! You are the intercessor on the Day of Judgment.' Then that light prostrated, rose, and from it, 124,000 droplets dripped. God created a prophet from each droplet. When the lights of the prophets were perfected, they all circled around the light of Muhammad, just as pilgrims circle around the Kaaba." [Majlisi, p. 27]

Universality and Vicegerency of the Perfect Human

The universality and vicegerency of the perfect human can be explained as follows: The perfect human is the manifestation of the Greatest Name of God, while other beings are manifestations of the other general and specific names of God. On the other hand, it is known that the Greatest Name encompasses all other names and is present within them. Therefore, by the correspondence of the manifest and the manifestation, it must be said that the perfect human encompasses all beings and pervades them. In fact, the truth is that the realities of the universe are manifestations of the reality of the perfect human. For this reason, the people of gnosis have referred to the external world as the "Great Human."

Imam Ali (peace be upon him) has said in a sermon:

"I am the Pen, the Preserved Tablet, the Throne, the Footstool, the seven heavens, and the earth."

Knowledge and Power

Since the perfect human is the vicegerent of God and God is All-Knowing:

"Indeed, Allah is Knowing of all things" and All-Powerful: "Indeed, Allah is over all things competent," the perfect human is also the manifestation of God's two names, Al-Alim (All-Knowing) and Al-Qadir (All-Powerful). Hence, the scope of their knowledge is so vast that it includes:

Knowledge of the unseen: "He is Knower of the unseen, and He does not disclose His unseen to anyone except whom He has approved of messengers."

Observation of the kingdom: "Thus We showed Abraham the realm of the heavens and the earth..."

Proximity and Wilayah

The perfect human surpasses everyone in every field and domain: "And no bird can reach it." He is the closest to God: "The foremost are the foremost; they are the ones who are near." Therefore, there is no intermediary between him and God: "Then He drew near and bowed down, and was at a distance of two bow-lengths or closer." Rather, he himself is the intermediary for others, and the blessings of existence and his perfections flow from the waterfall of his being to the creatures: "The flood descends from me." For this reason, the guardianship and governance of others are entrusted to him: "Indeed, your protector is Allah and His Messenger, and those who believe, those who establish the prayer and give the zakat while bowing." As the guardian of God, he also has the right to legislate: "And I have made lawful for you some of what was forbidden to you." "All food was lawful for the Children of Israel except what Israel had made unlawful for himself." He also has the right to execute and govern: "O David, indeed We have made you a successor upon the earth, so judge between the people with truth." "So judge between them by what Allah has revealed." And he has the right to control the beings of the world: "And We subdued for him the wind, blowing by his command, gently wherever he directed, and the devils, every builder and diver, and others bound together in chains."

Selection and Excellence

The attributes and perfections of the perfect human are all based on God's grace and divine designation, and neither his person nor his acquisition of them involves any intervention on his part. Words such as Istifa' (selection): "Indeed, Allah selected Adam, Noah, the family of Abraham, and the family of Imran over the worlds," Tafdhil (excellence), Ijtiba' (choosing), and Hidayah (guidance): "And Isma'il, and Al-Yasa, and Yunus, and Lot, and all of them We preferred over the worlds, and of their forefathers, descendants, and brothers, and We chose them and guided them to a straight path," Ikhlas (sincerity): "And remember Our servant, Abraham, Isaac, and Jacob, possessors of strength and vision. Indeed, We chose them with an exclusive remembrance of the abode," and Tathir (purification): "Indeed, Allah only intends to remove impurity from you, O People of the Household, and to purify you with a thorough purification" all support this notion with their specific spiritual weight, considering their attribution to God. Thus, Imam Reza (peace be upon him) in his famous narration about the recognition of the Imam says: The Imam, without any role of his own, possesses all virtues and merits: "He is endowed with all excellence without any request or acquisition, but it is an exclusive grace from the Giver of grace." Therefore, others who are not examples of the perfect human cannot attain his level through their own striving and seeking: "And no bird can reach me," "And indeed, you cannot do this." However, everyone is obligated to move along his path and, according to their capacities, strive to draw closer to him and benefit from his perfections and attributes: "But assist me with piety, diligence, chastity, and truthfulness." It is obvious that the value and rank of each person depends on how close they are to the perfect human, and their own effort will determine this: "And that man will have only what he strives for."

Leadership and Imamate

The perfect human, with the virtues and perfections granted by God—like a ruler that is straight and becomes the measure of straightness for other lines—is a creation of God: "Indeed, we are the creations of our Lord" and "My Lord has disciplined me, and He has perfected my discipline." They are the tangible manifestation of the straight path: "We are the Straight Path." Such an individual can serve as a model and guide for others, becoming their Imam and leader: "And [mention] when Abraham was tried by his Lord with commands and he fulfilled them. [Allah] said, 'Indeed, I will make you a leader for the people.'"

The perfect human is the Imam of all in all matters, and with God's permission, serves as an intercessor and guide for those journeying toward God: "Who is it that can intercede with Him except by His permission?" All human beings are obligated to seek nearness to God through them: "Seek the means [of nearness] to Him." Their words, actions, and qualities should be the standard by which people measure their own. "We are the just scales." Believers are commanded to obey them and avoid disobedience: "O you who have believed, obey Allah and obey the Messenger and those in authority among you,"

"O you who have believed, respond to Allah and to the Messenger when he calls you to that which gives you life,"

"And whoever disobeys Allah and His Messenger and transgresses His limits – He will put him into the Fire to abide eternally therein."

Since they are God's vicegerents, obedience to them equates to obedience to God: "Whoever obeys the Messenger has obeyed Allah." Disobedience to them is disobedience to God. In Surah Al-Ahzab (33:56), God commands believers to send blessings upon the perfect human, as He and His angels do:

"Indeed, Allah and His angels send blessings upon the Prophet. O you who have believed, ask [Allah to confer] blessings upon him and ask [Him to grant him] peace."

This command encourages believers to draw closer to the perfect human, obey their commands, and be saved from deviation and misguidance. Some commentators rightly believe that the perfect human does not benefit from the blessings sent by believers, just as God does not gain from the worship of His servants. Rather, it is the believers who, through worship and blessings upon the perfect human, align themselves with the flow of divine grace and the vicegerent of God, thereby receiving more infinite blessings.

In Ziyarat Jami'a Kabira, sending blessings upon the Ahl al-Bayt (peace be upon them) and adhering to their guardianship is regarded as a means for perfecting character, purifying the soul, and expiating sins.

According to a narration, Gabriel (peace be upon him) informed the Prophet (peace be upon him and his family) that whoever sends blessings upon him, God will bless them tenfold, erase ten of their sins, and record ten good deeds for them.

Similarities with the Gnostic System

Although the concept of the perfect human originates in Islamic mysticism and has Islamic roots, its resemblance to the Gnostic system cannot be overlooked. In Gnostic traditions and ancient religions, concepts like the Primordial Human in Mazdakism, the Adam Kadmon in Kabbalah, and the Primordial Man in Manichaeism are variations of this thought.

The idea of humans being created in the image of God, as mentioned in the Old Testament, and the notion of prophets like Noah being perfect in the same text, reflect a familiarity in the Judeo-Christian world with the idea of divine and God-like humans. This perspective was also present in Christian philosophy during the Middle Ages. Therefore, the perfect human is someone who has attained perfection and become like God, in contrast to the imperfect human who, due to the lack of perfection, bears no resemblance to God.

In the Perspective of Hallaj

At the end of the 3rd century AH, Husayn ibn Mansur Hallaj presented the concept of the Perfect Man both in the ideal personality of the Prophet Muhammad (peace and blessings be upon him) and in the realm of humanity and the universe. It is said that he believed in a "God-like human" or a "human-like God," and his interpretation of the term Takwin (Kun, "Be") aligned

with the understanding of the divine word in the Gnostic system. [Bertels, 1356, 38] [Noss, 1370, p. 759]

In his interpretation of "Khuluq Azeem" (sublime character), Hallaj states: The character of Muhammad (peace be upon him) was "sublime" because he neither settled for human morals nor stopped at divine attributes but became aware of the Divine Essence and annihilated his own essence within it. [Sulami, 1369, p. 286]

Furthermore, in his interpretation of verse 35 of Surah An-Nur, Hallaj expressed belief in the pre-eternity (azaliyah) of Muhammad (peace be upon him), asserting that among all lights, there was no light more luminous or ancient than the light of Muhammad (peace be upon him), a light whose existence preceded nonexistence.

On the other hand, Hallaj believed in Union (Ittihad) and the unity of being ('Ayn al-Jam'), positing that through spiritual and physical asceticism, a person could reach a state where the spirit of God descends into them. This elevates them to a position where everything becomes subjugated to them, and their decree becomes synonymous with God's decree. [Massinon, 1366, p. 57]

In the Perspective of Niffari

In his works Al-Mawaqif and Al-Mukhatabat, Niffari offers a profound portrayal of a human who can be a companion (Jalis) of God. According to him, the companion of God represents the soul and essence of existence because God, by endowing this individual with His attributes, has given them a power that enables them to dominate the world on His behalf. This companion is directly connected to the Divine without any intermediary and, by embodying divine attributes, imparts meaning to the world and acts within it. [Noya, 1373, p. 324]

Niffari's depiction of the companion of God bears a striking resemblance to Ibn Arabi's concept of the Perfect Man. This similarity is further highlighted by Afif al-Din Tilmisani, who interpreted the "companion of God" in Niffari's works as equivalent to Ibn Arabi's Perfect Man. [Noya, 1373, p. 323-324]

In the Perspective of Ibn Arabi

Such mystical reflections on prophethood and the ideal human existed in Islamic mysticism before Ibn Arabi, but he firmly established the discourse on the Perfect Man in Islamic mystical anthropology and cosmology during the late 6th and early 7th centuries AH. He integrated it into his concept of the unity of existence (Wahdat al-Wujud), depicting it in the forms of the Prophet (Nabi) and the Saint (Wali), as well as the divine vicegerency (Khilafah). Ibn Arabi regarded the most significant and sublime manifestation of the Divine as the archetypal human being, who is none other than Adam and the Divine Word (Kalimat Ilahiyyah), making him the Perfect Man. [Arabi, 1373, p. 324]

In a metaphorical expression, Ibn Arabi likens this archetype of creation to a "seal" (Tughra) that follows the Basmala ("In the Name of God"). Through this analogy, Ibn Arabi illustrates the Perfect Man as the "First Determination" (Ta'ayyun Awwal). [Arabi, 1373, p.324]

This Perfect Man encompasses all divine truths and the realities of existence (Haqa'iq Kawniyyah). As such, he is a universal being (Kawn Jami') and the Comprehensive Word (Kalima Jami'a). [Arabi, 1990, p. 13-14]

Nasafi's Perspective

In Nasafi's view, humanity is divided into two categories: the perfect human and the imperfect human. The perfect human is one who is complete in Sharia (law), Tariqa (path), and Haqiqa (truth), or in other words, someone who is perfect in good words, good deeds, good morals, and comprehensive knowledge. [Arabi, 1990, p. 4]

As observed, Nasafi's definition of the perfect human borrows terms commonly used in ancient Iranian thought. The names he assigns to the perfect human also bear no connection to the names associated with the concept in Ibn Arabi's works or those of his followers. Nasafi's names for the perfect human can be traced back to the foundational elements of Iranian philosophy. These include titles such as leader, wise one, universal cup, world-reflecting mirror, great elixir, supreme remedy, Khidr, the master of time, and others. [Arabi, 1990, p. 4-5]

Nasafi views attaining the rank of the perfect human as the ultimate aspiration for mystic seekers but does not consider the existential or innate aspects of this matter, as seen in Ibn Arabi's teachings. Nonetheless, Nasafi believes that the perfect human is akin to the heart of the universe. Just as there is one heart in a person, in the world, there is one perfect human who becomes a beacon. When one passes away, another individual with virtuous words, deeds, and morals takes their place. [Arabi, 1990, p. 5]

The perfect human strives earnestly to familiarize humanity with good principles and laws and to remove evil and dishonesty from the world. [Arabi, 1990, p. 6-7]

However, Nasafi's perfect human lacks worldly power and lives in hardship. While they are complete in knowledge and understanding, they remain incomplete in terms of power and worldly success. [Arabi, 1990, p. 8]

Occasionally, the perfect human may occupy the position of a ruler or king and wield power. Yet, even then, their helplessness and misfortune outweigh their authority. [Arabi, 1990, p. 7-8]

Comparing Ibn Arabi's Teachings with Nasafi's Views

A comparison between the teachings of Ibn Arabi's school of thought and Nasafi's views on the perfect human reveals that Nasafi does not attribute the attainment of human perfection to any supra-sensory quality such as the Reality of Muhammad (Haqiqat al-Muhammadiyah). He considers prophets and saints to be among perfect humans, but also regards anyone who achieves perfection in Sharia, Tariqa, and Haqiqa as a perfect human, implicitly including himself in this category. [Arabi, 1990, p. 10]

Accordingly, Nasafi's perfect human, apart from prophets, is comparable to a Sufi master or spiritual leader who has reached perfection through mystical practice and knowledge of Sharia, Tariqa, and Haqiqa. However, upon realizing that worldly life is marked by compulsion and misfortune, this perfect human turns away from the world, embraces seclusion, adopts contentment, and prefers anonymity. In this state, they are characterized by freedom and are referred to as the free perfect human. [Arabi, 1990, p. 8-9]

Nasafi also explores the concept of the perfect human from another perspective. He posits that the Essence of Oneness is a singular being with both an inner and outer aspect. Its inner aspect is a unified light that is the soul of the universe, and everything in the universe emanates from this light. Its outer aspect is also a manifestation of the same light. The singular existence of the Truth, through the manifestation of this light, created the universe as its mirror and reflection, wherein multiplicity appeared. Although all beings are mirrors and reflections of this light, it is the human being who most perfectly reflects this light, like a universal cup or a world-reflecting mirror, and is the ultimate purpose of creation. [Arabi, 1990, p. 249-252]

This dimension of the perfect human differs from the interpretations provided by Ibn Arabi and his commentators and is more closely tied to the philosophy of light in Iranian thought, though Nasafi attributes it to the views of the naturalists (Dahriyya). [Nasafi, 1360, p. 82]

Jalal al-Din Rumi's Perspective

Jalal al-Din Rumi was undoubtedly familiar with the discussions surrounding Ibn Arabi's concept of the perfect human. His references to the Universal Intellect [Moulavi, 1363, p. 1109, 277, 978] align with the Reality of Muhammad in Ibn Arabi's philosophy. The notion of creating humans in the image of God [Nikolson, 1374, p. 13] and attributing God's qualities to humans to the extent that their hand becomes the "hand of God," capable of transforming kufr (disbelief) into din (faith) [Moulavi, 1363, p. 1609 and 1614] and the idea that such a person exists in every era, hidden yet present, both Mahdi and guide [Moulavi, 1363, p. 815-818] as well as the belief that the essence of this human being is the ultimate cause of creation, even though they are temporally the last of all beings, [Moulavi, 1363, p. 521-524] all indicate Rumi's acquaintance with the concept of the perfect human as proposed by Ibn Arabi. However, Rumi never fully embraced Ibn Arabi's views on the perfect human, as their foundational philosophies differ. Ibn Arabi sees only one existence—absolute existence—and ultimately views the perfect human as a manifestation of divinity. [Arabi, 1293, p. 81-82]

Rumi, on the other hand, rejects the doctrine of oneness of being (Wahdat al-Wujud). In his ontology, existence belongs solely to God Almighty, and humans do not share in divinity; their essence does not merge into an absolute unity with the Creator. [Moulavi, 1363, p. 1345-1355]

As such, while Rumi acknowledges human perfection, he does not use the term perfect human. Instead, he refers to the perfected individual as the man of God or the upright saint, a person whose individuality remains intact at every station. [Moulavi, 1363, p. 815-828]

From the mid-7th century AH / 13th century CE onwards, Ibn Arabi's theories were widely disseminated by his followers across the Islamic world, to the extent that most Sufi orders became acquainted with and adopted the concept of the perfect human. By the mid-8th century AH, it became rare to find a Sufi order in the Islamic world that did not incorporate Ibn Arabi's teachings on the perfect human in some form. [Gibb, 1367, p. 169]

Conclusion

Some believe that the term "Perfect Man" was first introduced into poetry and literature by Muhyiddin Ibn Arabi. Before him, such a term was not used in mystical literature. As we see, Hallaj Mansur spoke about individuals who attained the stages of perfection in his works and considered himself a seeker who had reached such a state. It is known that in the end, he sacrificed his life on this path.

Hallaj, referring to the Prophet's hadith "Indeed, Allah created Adam in His image" (ان الله (خلق آدم على صورته), highlighted the divine character of humans beyond their material and sensory attributes. Thus, he asserted that the human being is the only creature in the realm of existence endowed with a divine image. After Hallaj, Bayazid Bastami also used the phrase "Al-Kamilut-Tamam" ("Perfect in the truest sense") when discussing humans.

Many mystics have expressed their views on the concept of the "Perfect Man" and sought to explain it in their works.

Here, we aim to outline a few principles that form the basis of this concept:

1. The primary purpose of the creation of the world is the Perfect Man. If there were no Perfect Man, there would be no creation.

2. The Perfect Man was created as a mirror for the Divine Essence, so that the Divine Essence could manifest itself in the essence of the Perfect Man. This is because, according to a sacred hadith, Allah desired to be known.

3. Allah created the universe as a body and breathed its soul into it by creating the "Perfect Human." The "Perfect Human" is like the soul within the body of the universe.

4. Mystics believe that the only "Perfect Human" who can be the mirror of the Divine Essence is the Prophet Muhammad. According to the famous hadith, "If it were not for you, I would not have created the heavens" (لولاك لما خلقت افلاك), the primary purpose of the universe's creation is the Prophet Muhammad.

5. In the hadith, "The first thing Allah created was my light" (اول ما خلق الله نوري), it is stated that he has been the most perfect human in all periods of existence.

6. Since the Prophet is the first being created by Allah, as indicated by the above hadith, his soul has been breathed into the entire universe. Mystics believe that the "Perfect Human," who is the soul of the universe, encompasses everything in the universe. This idea can be found in the works of thinkers like Muhyiddin Ibn Arabi and Jami.

7. From the above, it can be concluded that the "Perfect Human" is identical to the "Reality of Muhammad" (Haqiqah Muhammadiyyah).

8. To explain the "Reality of Muhammad," metaphors such as "soul for the body," "pole for the center," "mirror," "light," "radiance," "candle," "lamp," "sun," and "moon" have been used. Mystics also note that other beings derive from the "Light of Muhammad" (Nur-e Muhammadi).

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